
Effective teaching strategies and pedagogical competence of foreign language teachers

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Annotation *The present article presents the analysis of the advantages of using effective teaching strategies in the process of teaching foreign language as well as the elements of pedagogical competence of foreign language teachers in higher education system. Moreover, the advantages of implementing modern pedagogical technologies in teaching foreign language have been analyzed. The author pays attention to such terms as self-education, self-study and self-improvement and demonstrates their interrelation in teaching process.*

Keywords *Teaching strategies, pedagogical competence, teaching process, pedagogical technologies, self-education, self-study and self-improvement, motivation*

Эффективные стратегии обучения и педагогическая компетентность преподавателей иностранных языков

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Аннотация *В настоящей статье анализируются преимущества использования обучающих стратегий, а также элементов педагогической компетенции в процессе обучения иностранному языку. Более того, приводится анализ преимуществ использования современных педагогических технологий, используемых в учебном процессе. Автор уделяет внимание таким понятиям, как самообразование, самообучение и саморазвитие и показывает их взаимосвязь в процессе обучения.*

Ключевые слова *Стратегии обучения, педагогическая компетенция, учебный процесс, педагогические технологии, самообразование, самообучение и саморазвитие*

Chet tillarni o'qitishda samarali ta'lim strategiyalari va o'qituvchining pedagogik kompetensiyasi

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Annotatsiya *Mazkur maqolada chet tili jarayonida samarali o'qitish strategiyalarning tahlili keltirilgan, shuningdek, oliy ta'lim o'qituvchilarning pedagogik kompetensiyasining elementlar tahlil qilingan. Bundan tashqari, chet tilini o'qitish jarayonida qo'llanilgan pedagogik texnologiyalarning samaradorligi tahlilga tortilgan. Muallif mustaqil ta'lim va o'z ustidan ishlash kabi masalalarni yoritib, ularning o'quv jarayonida bir-biriga bog'ligligini ko'rsatib bergan.*

Kalit so'zlar *O'qitish strategiyalar, pedagogik kompetensiya, o'quv jarayoni, pedagogik texnologiyalar, mustaqil ta'lim, o'z ustidan ishlash*

Today's education system demands that graduates strive for self-improvement, self-esteem, self-development and self-actualization. All of this becomes possible due to the implementation of new educational technologies in the educational process. These

practical requirements must be done through the integrated efforts of all participants in the educational process and be based on the triad of "self-study – self-education – self-improvement" (Stolyarova, 2009; 180) (see scheme 1).

Scheme 1. *The main types of educational process*

Successful foreign language teaching requires not only the integration of proven modern teaching technologies into the educational process but also the implementation of learning activities using active learning methods: business games, role-playing games, debates, group exercises, creative tasks, etc. Although the creation and use of automated learning tasks based on computer technology is promising, it should be noted that no computer can replace a teacher.

The use of modern teaching technologies to develop students' thinking is aimed at:

- evaluating and modeling the material being studied;
- clearly and accurately developing a mechanism for achieving established goals;
- anticipating alternative ways to achieve goals and the long-term consequences of each;
- analyzing the "internal" and "external" results of each alternative;
- organically combining, coordinating, and integrating various types of activities (Vyunov, 2009; 169).

The teacher plays a significant role in teaching how to use various strategies in the teaching process. The opinion expressed by J. Wills is presented below:

- *task planning* – students can practice using this strategy before performing the task. The teacher can also determine whether students have understood the task by asking questions;
- *using worldview knowledge in anticipating responses* – preparing students for their speech activity by assimilating the topic and also facilitating the memorization of additional thematic information;
- *using linguistic knowledge in anticipating responses* – gap-filling exercises contribute to the development of this strategy;
- *monitoring the listening process* – the teacher can develop this strategy by asking a series of questions about students' understanding or lack of understanding while listening, analyzing the direct or incorrect formulation of

listeners' answers, or pausing when reaching the same idea;

- *selecting the most important ideas during listening* – the teacher can apply this strategy during teaching, using more precise details or exercises designed to listen for details;
- *record the necessary data while listening* – use keywords and briefly jot down important information;
- *compare the students' answers with each other*, as each student may understand and absorb information differently while listening;
- *written or oral presentation* of the information heard (Wilson, 2008; 36).

If learning materials that correspond to the modern form of the language are used during the learning process, the quality of students' communicative skills in a foreign language will significantly improve, which, in turn, will allow future professionals to participate in real-life intercultural communication.

The international language learning standard, according to the CEFR, includes: 1) listening; 2) reading; 3) writing; 4) speaking.

To develop listening skills, students listen to a specific audio recording or film appropriate to their level, and are then asked a series of questions that must be answered based on the content of the audio recording. Students are also given words from the text they heard, and must memorize them and fill in the blanks in the written text. When developing speaking skills, a series of questions is asked based on students' knowledge level, and they are given time to think through their answers. Any interesting topic can serve as a topic of conversation, for example, "happiest day," "best friend," "life's dream," etc. When developing reading skills, students are given a text of a certain difficulty level, which can contain from 200 to 2000 characters, depending on their language proficiency. When developing writing skills, students are given specific essay topics. The topic should be

problematic, so that students can not only describe it but also express their point of view and propose solutions. When developing writing skills, attention should be paid to grammar rules, sentence structure, and standard written formulas, wise word choice, and careful thought about the method of presentation.

Given the innovative processes occurring in the education system, particularly in the field of foreign language teaching, it should be noted that motivational methods are being thoroughly researched by many scholars, psychologists, and educators. Numerous articles, monographs, and books are being published, and practical proposals and recommendations are being developed to promote the development and improvement of this field.

Today, thanks to the dynamic development of global technology, information technology, and the growing popularity of various translation programs, including electronic dictionaries, students may feel that it is not necessary to develop translation skills and enrich their vocabulary. This, in turn, creates problems in such areas as language structure, lexical meaning, and the development of language skills. From the late 20th century to the early 21st century, it became clear that both scholars and educators recognized that vocabulary is of paramount importance in communication and that the importance of language learners' vocabulary is extremely important in the development of communicative competence (Bogaards, 2001; 321). Of course, not only lexical competence but also all linguistic competencies (grammatical, phonetic) are equally important for the development of language proficiency. However, since it is quite difficult to cover all linguistic competencies in a single activity, teachers should combine different types of work to simultaneously develop all linguistic competencies.

Various sources explain lexical competence and vocabulary that is, a specific

person's stock of words and expressions, the stock of commonly used words belonging to a social class or a specific field of activity as "possession and use of vocabulary." Lexical competence is the ability to understand and use words in speech. Lexical competence is an aspect of both linguistic and communicative competence.

Scholars define vocabulary as a mental property and process of productive word formation, arguing that it includes not only words but also phrases and set expressions, proverbs, and clichés. Considering that linguistic units of different levels are used as unified systemic elements in speech activity, the word is the most active unit in the communication process and has the ability to perform various speech functions, i.e., to create a verbal message. The semantics of lexical units allows grammatical forms and structures to be imbued with the content necessary to convey a complete thought. It is emphasized that vocabulary, unlike grammar, expresses a specific character, individualizes it, in other words, imbues it with a specific meaning (Mirolyubova, 2010; 165).

Learning words is a complex process. The lexicon of modern Indo-European languages consists of up to half a million words. Foreign language learners need to know 400-500 words to communicate, while educated individuals need to know 3,000-5,000 words for oral and written speech, listening comprehension, and reading. According to research by S.Thornbury, native speakers of a foreign language only need to know approximately 2,000 words to communicate. Some researchers argue that 3,000 words are necessary for communication, while others emphasize the need to learn 5,000 words (Thornbury, 2002; 20-21).

According to the Council of Europe's recognized international standards (CEFR), "Language Proficiency: Teaching, Learning and Assessment" are designed to gradually

advance students' proficiency in a foreign language to level C1. The practical application of this standard constitutes a systematic program for teaching foreign languages. Every pedagogical software tool created today is designed to fully realize this goal. In accordance with this requirement, the software being developed facilitates effective foreign language learning at any time convenient for students.

According to teachers, the following components of a teacher's pedagogical competence play a crucial role in the learning and development of foreign languages:

- teaching forms and methods;
 - the level of the teacher's professionalism;
 - communication skills that enable high-level professional-pedagogical dialogue;
 - ability to maintain a level of professional integrity in assessing and evaluating students' knowledge;
 - ability to conduct oneself with dignity as a teacher;
 - a friendly and respectful attitude toward students;
 - student motivation;
 - ability to create a working atmosphere.
- To develop positive motivation, it's advisable to focus on completing specific tasks without focusing on every student error (Ellis, 2009; 5).

Therefore, a student-centered approach is essential in developing foreign language competencies. It allows students to be continually informed about their knowledge, enabling them to take responsibility for their learning. Furthermore, students are encouraged to work collaboratively, teach each other, and share their knowledge and experiences. However, this does not relieve teachers of their responsibility; it requires the creation of an interactive foreign language learning environment and the integration of a student-centered approach to teaching, tailored to the needs and abilities of students.

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